

A Double Factorial based novel proof for the infinitude of primes from a Euclid Family Proofs

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Abstract

Let $p_1 = 2 < p_2 < \dots < p_k$ be all primes and define

$$P = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i.$$

Consider the even double factorial

$$P!! = 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots P.$$

We show that $P!!+1$ has a prime divisor that does not belong to $\{p_1, \dots, p_k\}$, that will yield a valid novel proof of infinitude of primes from the Euclid family proofs for the infinitude of primes.

1 Double Factorial

For $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ the double factorial is defined by

$$n!! = \begin{cases} n(n-2)(n-4) \cdots 2, & n \text{ even,} \\ n(n-2)(n-4) \cdots 1, & n \text{ odd.} \end{cases}$$

In particular, for $n = 2m$,

$$(2m)!! = 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots (2m) = \prod_{j=1}^m (2j).$$

2 Divisibility Structure

Let $p_1 = 2 < p_2 < \dots < p_k$ denote all primes and define

$$P = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i.$$

Since $p_1 = 2$, the integer P is even, and therefore

$$P!! = 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \cdots P.$$

Lemma 1. For every prime p_i , we have $p_i \mid P!!$.

Proof. We have

$$P!! = \prod_{j=1}^{P/2} (2j).$$

If $p_1 = 2$, clearly $2 \mid P!!$.

If $p_i > 2$, then since P contains both factors 2 and p_i ,

$$2p_i \leq P.$$

Thus $2p_i$ appears among the factors

$$2, 4, 6, \dots, P.$$

Hence $p_i \mid 2p_i \mid P!!$. □

3 Infinitude of Primes

Theorem 1. There are infinite prime numbers.

Proof. Let the set of primes be finite:

$$\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k\}.$$

Let

$$P = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i, \quad N = P!! + 1.$$

By Lemma 1, each p_i divides $P!!$, hence

$$p_i \nmid N.$$

Therefore

$$\gcd(N, p_i) = 1 \quad \text{for all } i.$$

Two possibilities arise.

1. N is prime. Then $N > p_k$, contradicting that p_k is the largest prime.
2. N is composite. Let q be a prime divisor of N . Since $q \mid N$ but $q \nmid P!!$, we have

$$q \notin \{p_1, \dots, p_k\}.$$

Both cases contradict the assumption that the set of primes is finite.

Hence infinitely many primes exist. □

4 Relation to Euclid-Type Constructions

Let

$$P = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i.$$

Euclid's classical proof considers

$$P + 1.$$

More generally, any integer M satisfying

$$p_i \mid M$$

for all i can be used to construct

$$M + 1$$

to obtain a new prime divisor.

The present construction uses

$$M = P!!,$$

where the divisibility arises from the even progression

$$2, 4, 6, \dots, P.$$

5 Conclusion

The number

$$N = P!! + 1$$

cannot be divisible by any of the assumed finite set of primes. Therefore N must introduce a new prime divisor.

This yields a Euclid-type argument establishing the infinitude of primes using the structure of the even double factorial.